

Research Article

Effect of Salt Applications on Water Absorption Capacity (WAC) of Mushroom Varieties Obtained in Akure, Nigeria

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Abstract

This work was researched to study the effect of different salts concentrations on the WAC of mushroom varieties obtained in Akure, Nigeria. From the results obtained, The WAC of all samples in water differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) with Chlorophyllum molybditis having the highest while Pleurotus ostreatus the lowest while, the WAC of the fungus in the different salts at different concentrations differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the order of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaNO}_3 > \text{NaNO}_2 > \text{NaCl}$. Our results compare favourably with other research works on food formulations. It was noticed that the WAC value of samples decreased as the concentration of the salts increased which may be depended on the type of salt and effects of salt with the cation and anion species involved. In conclusion, it was observed that WAC concentrations were influenced by the different salts concentrations. Therefore formulations involving the use of mushrooms will have to take into consideration different salts concentrations.

KEYWORDS: fungi, Water Absorption capacity, salt concentrations, functional properties, Akure

Received: 28 March 2021

Accepted: 22 May 2021

Introduction

Edible mushrooms have for a long time been recognized not only as a delicacy but also for their use as food in man's diets (Ndamitso and Abulude, 2013; Abulude *et al.*, 2004). They are rich sources of protein, lipids, amino acids, glycogen, vitamins, and mineral salts (Okwulehie and Odunze, 2004). According to Adeyeye *et al.* (2008), the mineral salts contents of mushrooms are superior to those of meat and fish and nearly twice those of most common vegetables. These fungi have also been mentioned for their medicinal values (Selvi *et al.*, 2007; Abulude, 2013).

Nigeria is a country of many tribes among which are the Hausas in the North, Yorubas in the South West, Urhobo in the Mid - West and the Ibos in the East and each of these tribes has recognized mushrooms for many years using a number of them for various economic and medicinal purposes (Ukoima *et al.*, 2009).

Mushroom samples identified for the study are *Lentinus subnudus* Berk (M₁), *Chlorophyllum molybditis* (M₂), *Volvariella esculenta* (M₃), *Coprinus tramentarius* (M₄), *Pleurotus ostreatus* Jacq (M₅), *Termitomyces microcarpus* (M₆), and *Pleurotus pulmonarius*. They are useful as foods, medicine, drying fabrics, bioremediation, and traditional worships (Abulude, 2004; Kettawan *et al.*, 2011).

Although the nutritional and medicinal values of mushrooms have long been recognized (Manzi *et al.*, 2001; Kettawan *et al.*, 2011), in the past, their consumption has mainly been confined to rural Nigeria. However, in recent times, their consumption has assumed greater importance in the diets of both rural and urban dwellers. For example, they are being marketed along major highways and urban centres where the trade now booms. It is conceivable that the increased demand for mushrooms is predicated upon the phenomenal rise in the costs of the conventional sources of animal protein sources like beef, pork, chicken, fish, and eggs.

According to Damoradan *et al.*, 2010, water absorption capacity (WAC) is the addition of water or an aqueous solution to material, which is followed by centrifugation and the determination of the quantity of water retained by the material. WAC at high values maintain the moisture contents of the product processed, it improves the quality of products and also maintains the characteristics throughout shelf-life and when the product is subjected to high temperatures and freezing (Köhn *et al.*, 2015).

The ultimate success of utilizing plant proteins as ingredients depends largely upon the beneficial qualities they impact on foods which by extension depend largely on their functional properties. The functional properties of plant protein have been reported to be dependent upon the chemical characteristics inherent in the seed (Aremu *et al.*, 2009). The significance of salts has been reported in the food industry

(Ogungbemile *et al.*, 2009). The relative effects of cations and anions are influenced by the intensity of their surface charge which is influenced by the atomic radii. At this salt concentration, electrostatic interactions are of little importance with regards to the number of water bounds of protein because competition of the ions and proteins for water becomes predominant (Ogungbemile *et al.*, 2009). There is a gap in the literature regarding studies assessing the WAC of mushroom samples. There is a need to provide information for the food industry to assist in the choice of salts and appropriate concentrations in the development of new food formulations (meat and plant products).

In this study, mushroom species would be prepared with different salts concentrations and the effects of the salts concentrations on the functional properties would be studied.

The objective of the Study

To determine the effects of different concentrations of NaCl, Na₂SO₄, CH₃COONa, NaNO₂, and NaNO₃ on the WAC of mushroom varieties consumed in South West of Nigeria.

Materials and Methods

Source of Materials and Sample Pre-treatment

The mushrooms; *Lentinus subnudus* Berk (M₁), *Chlorophyllum molybdites* (M₂), *Volvariella esculenta* (M₃), *Coprinus tramentarius* (M₄), *Pleurotus ostreatus* Jacq (M₅), *Termitomyces microcarpus* (M₆), and *Pleurotus pulmonarius* (M₇) were collected from Federal College of Agriculture campus, Akure, Ondo State, Southwest part of Nigeria. The bad or rotten samples were sorted out. The samples were oven-dried at 65°C for 72 hours and were then pound into a powdered form using porcelain pestle and mortar. The milled samples were then sieved with a 2mm mesh sized sieve and stored in waterproof polyethylene bags at room temperature for further analysis.

Determination of Water Absorption Capacity (WAC)

The water absorption capacity was determined using the modified method of Ogungbemile *et al.*, (2009). One gram of sample was taken in triplicates in test tubes and mixed with 10cm³ of distilled water on a mixer and kept at room temperature for 30 minutes. It was later centrifuged at a speed of 20,000 rpm for 30 minutes and the volume of the supernatant taken using a 10 cm³ graduated cylinder. The density of water was assumed to be 1g/cm³. The excess water absorbed by the flour in each case was expressed as the percentage of water bound by 100g sample.

Statistical analysis

Data obtained were generated in triplicates and analyzed using Minitab 16 statistical software. The mean, standard deviation, and one-way analysis of variance with Duncan Multiple Range test at 95% confidence or $p < 0.05$ were determined.

Results and Discussion

The results for WAC in water are presented in Table 1. The WAC of all samples in water differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) with *Chlorophyllum molybditis* having the highest while *Pleurotus ostreatus* the lowest. The results for WAC in *Chlorophyllum molybditis* are presented in Table 2. The WAC of the fungus in the different salts at different concentrations differed significantly ($p < 0.05$) in the order of $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa} > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaNO}_3 > \text{NaNO}_2 > \text{NaCl}$. The WAC of *V. esculenta* in the different salt concentrations differed significantly ($p < 0.05$). Table 3 shows the strength of the different concentration from the highest to the lowest. *V. esculenta* - $\text{CH}_3\text{COONa} > \text{NaNO}_3 > \text{NaNO}_2 > \text{Na}_2\text{SO}_4 > \text{NaCl}$. Same observations were obtained in Tables 4 – 8 (As the concentrations of the different salts increases, there were decreases in WAC).

Water Absorption Capacity (WAC) values of the samples were as shown in Tables 1 – 8. These varied from $180.48 \pm 20.08\%$ (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) to $430.48 \pm 20.46\%$ (*Coprinus tramentarius*) for all salts. The lowest value in this work was lower than that reported for the three species of mushrooms by Aremu *et al.*, (2009) but the highest value obtained in this work was higher than $390.00 \pm 5.00\%$ reported for *Ganoderma spp.* These values were also higher than those reported for Lima bean flours by Aremu *et al.* (2009). These tables showed a decrease in WAC of samples as the concentration of the salts increased which is depended on the type of salt. This may be because the effects of salt vary with the cation and anion species involved (Ogungbemile *et al.*, 2009). The higher water absorption capacity of mushroom species compared to Bambara groundnut flour 221.83 and 281.35% recorded by Eltayeb *et al.* (2011) may be due to the higher polar amino acid residues of proteins having an affinity for water molecules (Yusuf *et al.*, 2008). The major chemical compositions that enhance the water absorption capacity of flours are proteins and carbohydrates since these constituents contain hydrophilic parts, such as polar or charged side chains (Lawal and Adebawale, 2004).

The ultimate success of utilizing plant proteins as ingredients depends largely upon the beneficial qualities they impact to foods which depend largely on their functional properties (Ndamitso and Abulude, 2014). Functional properties are intrinsic physicochemical characteristics that affect the behaviour of properties in food systems during processing, manufacturing, storage, and preparation (Abdel Rahman *et al.*, 2011) Nutritional and functional qualities of protein are largely determined by its amino acid content and nitrogen solubility (Eltayeb *et al.*, 2011). The critical functional

properties necessary in protein ingredients include gelation, emulsion, and foam formation, which are important for the function of proteins in food systems. Other paramount functionalities are proteins solubility, water, and fat absorption capacity (Abdel Rahman *et al.*, 2011). These characteristics are influenced by salt concentration during food formulation in the modern food industry (Andualem and Gessesse, 2013).

Table 1: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity (WAC) of Selected Varieties of Mushrooms in Water (%)

Samples	WAC
M ₁	340.24±20.10 ^c
M ₂	380.38±19.87 ^d
M ₃	380.42±20.03 ^d
M ₄	260.28±20.02 ^b
M ₅	180.48±20.08 ^a
M ₆	200.22±20.20 ^a
M ₇	260.24±19.74 ^b

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Water Absorption Capacity of *Chlorophyllum molybditis* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different Salts	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	Salts CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	340.44±19.95 ^a	420.55±2.05 ^c	240.82±20.10 ^{ab}	280.56±20.00 ^a	320.35±19.90 ^b
4	320.54±20.15 ^a	240.21±19.85 ^a	240.11±20.00 ^{ab}	280.35±19.95 ^a	300.35±20.00 ^{ab}
6	340.61±20.00 ^a	280.49±20.10 ^b	240.73±20.00 ^{ab}	280.45±19.95 ^a	280.50±20.10 ^a
8	340.36±20.05 ^a	300.50±20.00 ^b	280.43±20.00 ^a	240.38±20.00 ^a	300.55±20.00 ^{ab}
10	326.98±23.15 ^a	293.79±23.01 ^b	247.08±23.11 ^{ab}	260.38±19.98 ^a	287.08±22.97 ^{ab}
12	340.39±20.07 ^a	287.06±23.11 ^b	240.38±22.15 ^{ab}	253.88±22.88 ^a	293.78±23.05 ^{ab}

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different ($p < 0.05$).

Table 3: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Volvariella esculenta* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	463.55±11.74 ^c	480.36±20.15 ^b	510.28±19.72 ^b	300.28±19.83 ^c	430.48±20.46 ^{ab}
4	440.34±19.84 ^c	400.48±20.18 ^a	460.15±19.82 ^{ab}	280.38±19.73 ^{bc}	428.42±20.07 ^{ab}
6	433.11±19.83 ^{ab}	360.13±20.19 ^a	460.29±20.28 ^{ab}	260.19±19.72 ^{ab}	410.26±20.10 ^a
8	430.39±19.81 ^{ab}	384.20±18.74 ^a	460.25±19.85 ^{ab}	252.45±19.62 ^{bc}	400.16±19.86 ^a
10	401.88±23.32 ^b	315.12±23.01 ^a	460.45±29.73 ^a	242.22±17.76 ^{ab}	400.52±10.18 ^a
12	361.99±17.83 ^a	311.95±22.31 ^a	410.45±29.73 ^a	200.35±19.97 ^a	400.59±19.50 ^a

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different (p < 0.05).

Table 4: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Coprinus tramentarius* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different Salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	460.11±20.16 ^d	460.44±19.75 ^b	460.25±20.38 ^a	325.11±15.53 ^d	440.22±19.67 ^c
4	400.19±20.29 ^{ab}	443.52±20.18 ^a	440.36±20.19 ^b	300.82±18.73 ^{bcd}	420.45±19.68 ^{bc}
6	400.35±20.28 ^{ab}	440.09±20.13 ^b	401.86±22.27 ^a	285.26±19.72 ^{abc}	380.36±19.71 ^{ab}
8	400.11±20.04 ^a	440.42±19.82 ^b	441.95±20.10 ^b	260.22±19.82 ^a	400.35±19.72 ^{abc}
10	420.34±20.15 ^{bc}	440.53±19.84 ^b	440.63±20.01 ^b	280.43±19.84 ^{ab}	420.48±10.18 ^{bc}
12	460.34±20.15 ^d	400.48±19.95 ^a	440.65±19.80 ^b	320.43±20.05 ^{cd}	360.59±19.50 ^a

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different (p < 0.05).

Table 5: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Pleurotus ostreatus* In Different Salt Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different Salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	340.51±20.10 ^b	340.42±20.07 ^{ab}	240.48±20.38 ^b	293.11±15.53 ^b	231.29±20.67 ^b
4	235.19±20.29 ^a	280.56±19.93 ^b	224.35±15.19 ^a	260.81±19.73 ^a	200.48±19.68 ^a
6	201.35±20.28 ^a	205.11±18.83 ^a	220.35±22.27 ^a	281.26±19.72 ^a	225.21±18.71 ^a
8	320.38±19.93 ^b	213.77±19.82 ^a	220.40±19.95 ^a	260.38±19.89 ^a	200.36±20.06 ^a
10	320.32±20.15 ^b	200.53±19.84 ^a	200.49±20.01 ^a	260.36±19.98 ^a	200.29±10.18 ^a
12	200.52±20.15 ^a	200.48±19.95 ^a	233.84±19.80 ^a	280.48±19.77 ^a	187.12±19.50 ^a

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different (p < 0.05).

Table 6: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Termitomyces microcarpus* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different Salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	345.51±20.00 ^{ab}	420.30±19.95 ^c	280.40±19.90 ^c	280.48±20.53 ^b	350.51±20.67 ^b
4	320.31±19.89 ^a	240.34±20.03 ^a	243.05±15.19 ^{ab}	280.81±19.73 ^b	300.41±19.68 ^{ab}
6	340.45±20.18 ^a	280.41±19.83 ^b	277.35±22.27 ^c	280.26±19.72 ^b	300.42±18.71 ^{ab}
8	340.38±19.93 ^a	300.48±20.82 ^b	240.45±19.95 ^a	240.38±19.89 ^a	300.49±20.06 ^{ab}
10	320.37±20.16 ^a	300.35±19.84 ^b	240.35±19.93 ^{ab}	260.55±19.98 ^{ab}	280.39±20.18 ^a
12	340.31±20.00 ^a	280.35±20.05 ^b	260.39±19.80 ^b	260.36±20.77 ^{ab}	300.39±19.50 ^{ab}

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different (p < 0.05).

Table 7: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Pleurotus pulmonarius* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Concentration of different Salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	360.04±19.90 ^a	360.54±20.95 ^{ab}	400.41±19.90 ^{ab}	280.48±20.53 ^{ab}	380.22±20.67 ^b
4	340.40±20.00 ^a	240.34±20.03 ^a	360.25±15.19 ^a	280.81±19.73 ^{ab}	360.25±19.68 ^{ab}
6	380.58±19.18 ^{bc}	340.45±20.83 ^a	360.42±22.27 ^a	280.26±19.72 ^{ab}	340.58±18.71 ^a
8	353.71±19.93 ^{ab}	326.95±20.82 ^a	280.35±19.95 ^a	240.38±19.89 ^{ab}	340.38±20.06 ^a
10	360.04±19.16 ^{ab}	340.55±19.94 ^a	260.56±19.93 ^a	260.55±19.98 ^a	380.22±20.18 ^b
12	362.49±23.57 ^{ab}	330.49±20.05 ^a	310.19±19.80 ^a	260.36±20.77 ^b	360.12±19.50 ^{ab}

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different (p < 0.05).

Table 8: The Results of Water Absorption Capacity of *Lentinus subnudus* In Different Salts Concentrations (%)

Conc. of Salts	Salts				
	NaNO ₂	NaNO ₃	CH ₃ COONa	NaCl	Na ₂ SO ₄
2	330.37±19.94 ^c	270.27±20.17 ^{ab}	300.52±19.90 ^b	300.41±20.53 ^{ab}	300.38±19.67 ^c
4	320.33±20.00 ^a	260.48±20.03 ^a	250.15±20.19 ^a	289.37±20.73 ^b	300.34±20.68 ^c
6	300.19±19.18 ^{bc}	240.34±20.17 ^b	240.39±19.27 ^a	260.23±19.72 ^a	280.19±20.71 ^{bc}
8	320.23±19.99 ^{ab}	300.22±19.82 ^a	240.35±19.95 ^a	260.34±20.17 ^a	260.44±20.06 ^{ab}
10	300.52±19.90 ^{ab}	240.37±19.99 ^a	260.29±19.93 ^a	280.51±19.98 ^{ab}	280.33±20.00 ^{bc}
12	300.55±20.57 ^{ab}	240.23±20.05 ^a	260.19±19.80 ^a	280.47±19.85 ^{ab}	280.28±19.50 ^{bc}

All values were expressed as averages of triplicate determinations ± the standard deviations and values bearing the same superscripts in the same row are significantly not different ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

The results like other researches showed that WAC concentrations were influenced by the different salts concentrations. Therefore, different food formulations (Soups, gravies, stir-fries and salads) involving the use of these organisms will have to take into consideration the effects of different salts concentrations to achieve the desired objectives.

References

- Abulude F.O, Adeyeye E.I., and Asaolu S. S. (2004). Metal levels in Mushrooms consumed in Southwestern Nigeria. *Advances in Food Sciences*. 26 (4): 155 – 158.
- Abulude, F. O (2013). Functional properties of selected mushroom varieties obtained in Akure, Southwest Nigeria as affected by different salts concentrations. Unpublished M. Tech Thesis. Federal University of Technology, Minna, Niger State, Nigeria.
- Abdel Rahman S. M. Eltayeb, Ali O. Ali, Azza A. Abou-Arab and Ferial M. Abu-Salem (2011). Chemical composition and functional properties of flour and protein isolate extracted from Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*). *African Journal of Food Science* Vol. 5(2), pp. 82 – 90
- Adeyeye, E.I., Adubiaro, H.A. and Awodola, O.J. (2008). Comparability of chemical composition and functional properties of shell and flesh of *Penaecus notabilis*. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 7 (6), 741 – 747.
- Aremu, M O., Basuk, Gyan, S. D., Goyal, A., Bhowmik, P. K. and Datta Banik, S. (2009). Proximate composition and functional properties of mushroom flours from *Ganoderma spp*, *Omphalotus olearius* (DC) sing and *Hebeloma mesphaeum* (Pers) Quels used in Nassarawa State, Nigeria. *Malaysian of Journal Nutrition*, 15 (2), 233-241.
- Anduaem B and Gessesse A (2013). Effects of Salt (NaCl) Concentrations on the Functional Properties of Defatted Brebra (*Millettia ferruginea*) Seed Flour. *Middle-East Journal of Scientific Research* 13 (7): 889-897. DOI: 10.5829/idosi.mejsr.2013.13.7.2791.
- Damoradan, S., Parkin, K.L. and Fennema, O. (2010). *Química de Alimentos de Fennema*. p.100-850. Porto Alegre: Artmed.
- Eltayeb, Abdel Rahman S. M., Ali, O. Ali, Abou-Arab, Azza A. and Abu-Salem, Ferial M. (2011). Chemical composition and functional properties of flour and protein isolate

extracted from Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*). *African Journal of Food Science*, 5(2), 82 – 90.

Kattawan, A., Chanlekha, K., Kongkachuichai, R., and Chaaroensiri, R. (2011). Effects of cooking on antioxidant activities and polyphenol content of edible mushrooms commonly consumed in Thailand. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 10 (11), 1094-1103.

Köhn, C.R., Fontoura, A.M., Kempka, A.P., Demiate, I.M., Kubota, E.H. and Prestes, R.C. (2015). Assessment of different methods for determining the capacity of water absorption of ingredients and additives used in the meat industry. *International Food Research Journal* 22 (1): 356-362.

Lawal OS and Adebowale KO (2004). Effect of acetylation and succinylation on solubility profile, water absorption capacity, oil absorption capacity and emulsifying properties of mucuna bean (*Mucuna pruriens*) protein concentrate. *Nahrung/Food*, 48(2): 129-136.

Manzi, P., Aguzzi, A., and Pizzoferrato., L. (2001). Nutritive value of mushrooms widely consumed in Italy. *Food Chemistry*, 73, 321 – 325.

Ndamitso M. and Abulude F. (2013). Nutritional assessment of some mushroom species, *Electronic Journal of Polish Agricultural Universities (EJPau)* 16(4), #11. Available
Online: <http://www.ejpau.media.pl/volume16/issue4/art-11.html>

Ndamitso, M.M and Abulude, F. O (2014). Effect of different salt concentrations on protein solubility of mushroom varieties obtained in Akure, Nigeria. *American Journal of Food and Nutrition*. Vol. 2, No. 1, 7-10.

Ogungbenle, H.N., Oshodi, A. A. and Oladimeji, M.O. (2009). The proximate and effect of salt applications on some functional properties of Quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*) flour. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 8 (1), 49 – 52.

Okwulehie, I.C. and Odunze, E.T. (2004): Evaluation of the Myco-chemical and Mineral Composition of Some Tropical Edible Mushroom. *Journal of Sustainable Agriculture and Environment*, 6 (1), 63-70.

Selvi, S., Uma, Devi P., Suja, S., Murugan, S. and Chinnarswamy, P. (2007). Comparison of non-enzymic antioxidant status of fresh and dried form of *Pleurotus florida* and *Calocybe indica*. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 6 (5), 468-471.

Ukoima, H.N., Ogbonnaya, L. O., Arikpo, G. E. and Ikpe, F. N. (2009). Cultural studies of mycelia of *Volvariella volvacea*, *Pleurotus tuber-regium* and *Pleurotus sajor caju* on different culture media. *Pakistan Journal of Nutrition*, 8 (7), 1052-1054.

Yusuf AA, Ayedun H and Sanni LO (2008). Chemical composition and functional properties of raw and roasted Nigerian benniseed (*Sesamum indicum*) and Bambara groundnut (*Vigna subterranean*). *Food Chem.*, 111: 277-282.